

Direct-To-Object printing (or DTO printing) is a distinct form of digital print that uses ultraviolet (UV), light to cure and dry ink almost as quickly as it is applied on a substrate. The UV printing process is unique. You can use flat or cylindrical substrates. It can be made of metals, acrylics, plastic, glass and canvas. As the UV ink is distributed onto the substrate, specialized ultraviolet lights within the printer are immediately applied to the material over the top of the ink, drying it and adhering it to the substrate.

Initially, UV printing was used to create gel nail polishes. A UV light is used after the gel polish has been applied to cure it onto the nails. It results in a fast-drying, flawless manicure. Eventually, however, the benefits of ultraviolet light applications expanded and began being used in commercial and industrial markets. This forms the foundation of UV printing services and the associated printing industry. You can use it to make flyers and leaflets, screen printing, labels, and bottle labels, just to name a few. UV printing is not unlike traditional printing. But the inks used <https://redboltlaser.com> as well the drying and curing methods are different. This is in addition the distinctive nature of printing technology.

Traditional printing uses solvent inks that are applied to a substrate and heated to cure it. Solvent-based solvent inks can evaporate, spread onto the substrate and then release volatile organic compound (VOCs). Unpleasant odor is produced by the heat used to cure solvent ink to substrate. Furthermore, the solvent inks are absorbed into the substrate, which can result in faded colors. Spray powders can also prevent ink from drying and offsetting, which can lead to a slow and tedious process. Due to the nature of the printing press, traditional printing can only be done on paper and other similar materials. It cannot be used on other materials such as metal, plastic, glass, or acrylic.

With UV printing, specialized UV inks are used. To cure ink onto the substrate, high-intensity LED UV lights are used instead of heat. The ink is spread onto the substrate by the ultraviolet light. As a result, the ink dries immediately, no matter what material (or materials) are used. Because the ink is dry almost immediately, it doesn't evaporate and cannot spread onto the printed material.

In addition to the quick-drying capabilities and the eco-friendliness of UV printing, this ultraviolet printing method and the associated form of ink transfer can also be used with various materials, including paper, plastic, foil, acrylic, foam, etc. The air is free from VOCs, ozone and toxic fumes. This feature is a great option for companies who value sustainability in their printing processes.

Imagine all the possibilities when digitally printing is possible on an item. Instead of using a sticker to attach to the object, you can imagine the possibilities. With DTO Direct-To-Object, printing in full color is applied directly to the item.